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Deliverable 2.9

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.9 overview

This report outlines the creation of climate velocity maps for the MPA Europe study area under future climate change scenarios using the approach described in **Deliverable 2.8** (Burrows *et al.*, 2025). Climate velocity, the rate and direction of spatial climate shifts over time (Burrows *et al.*, 2011; Devictor *et al.*, 2008) was calculated using the environmental layers established in **Deliverable 2.1** (Assis *et al.*, 2023), using projected maps of average sea surface temperature for mid- and end-of-century time periods (2040-2060 and 2080-2100 respectively) from ensemble predictions of Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) global climate models (Assis *et al.*, 2024). Future climate velocity maps will act as a reference for the prioritisation analysis focused on designing a Marine Protected Area (MPA) network to promote biodiversity conservation and blue carbon. Through this process, the most effective MPA networks covering 10% and 30% of European seas will be identified to maximise benefits for biodiversity, blue carbon, and their combined advantages.

Background

The velocity of climate change expresses the rate and direction of spatial shifts in climate over time (Burrows *et al.*, 2011; Devictor *et al.*, 2008) and has proved to be a useful and universal predictor of global shifts in species distributions in the ocean (Pinsky *et al.*, 2013; Poloczanska *et al.*, 2013, 2014). Climate velocity can also show how global patterns of biodiversity might change under climate warming (García Molinos *et al.*, 2016) and where geographical barriers might prevent or hinder the poleward spread of species through areas of newly suitable climate (Burrows *et al.*, 2014). The product has been widely used in global assessments of impacts of climate change on natural ecological systems (Poloczanska *et al.*, 2014) and on society and people (Pörtner *et al.*, 2023). Climate trajectories derived from velocity fields have useful implications for changes in biodiversity with climate, especially when their collective spatial behaviour is divided into classes, such as climate ‘sources’ and ‘sinks’ and areas of slow and rapid shifts. A summary of the implications of these classes is given in Table 1.

As part of Work Package 2 (Ecosystem and connectivity modelling) of MPA Europe, we aim to use maps of current and future climate velocity across European seas to assess how well a proposed MPA network will facilitate species range shifts responding to climate change, through the inclusion of present as well as future biodiversity. This **Deliverable 2.9** produces maps of velocity of climate change using projected climate change scenarios (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways, SSP) spanning from high mitigation (SSP1-1.9 matching the Paris Agreement) to business-as-usual scenarios (SSP5-8.5, ‘Fossil-fueled Development’ (Meinshausen *et al.*, 2020; Riahi *et al.*, 2017).

Methods

We used sea surface temperature data from Bio-Oracle 3.0 (Assis *et al.*, 2024) (<https://www.bio-oracle.org/>) for present day and projected future conditions of European seas (see Appendix Figure A1-A2). Climate velocities were calculated using the methods of Burrows *et al.* (2011, 2014) incorporated into an R library (García Molinos *et al.*, 2019), modified to produce maps of the velocity (speed and direction) of climate change. The model domain was chosen to include areas south of Europe where future conditions for European seas currently exist.

A complete set of climate velocity maps were produced using the 20-year average sea surface temperatures for 2000–2020 as the baseline for comparison of temperatures between 2000–2020 and projected sea surface temperatures in 2040–2060 and 2080–210 under each of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP1-1.9, SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0, SSP5-8.5, (Meinshausen *et al.*, 2020; Riahi *et al.*, 2017). SSP3-7.0 (‘Regional rivalry’), for example, represents expected warming under a radiative forcing of 7 w/m², leading to a global warming of about 4 to 5 °C above the preindustrial levels by 2100 in a world where nationalism and regional conflicts overshadow global issues (Böttinger & Kasang, 2025).

For velocity calculations, trends in temperature (°C/yr) for each 0.05-degree latitude-longitude grid cell were obtained using the differences between the two periods, divided by the duration between the two period mid points. Velocity of climate was thus determined as the ratio of the trend in temperature to the local spatial gradient of average temperatures across the two periods. Direction of climate velocity was derived from the direction of the local spatial gradients in temperature around

each grid cell. The sign of climate velocity reflects the sign of the trend in temperature: positive thermal velocities occur in areas of warming and negative thermal velocities in areas of cooling. Positive velocities are directed towards locally cooler areas while negative velocities are directed towards locally warmer areas.

Climate trajectories (Burrows *et al.*, 2014), the paths that points on isotherms are expected to follow over time were calculated using temperatures and velocities downscaled to 0.1-degree resolution from the original 0.05-degree resolution. Since trajectories follow local velocities, in areas of warming, positive velocities mean that trajectories show isotherm shifts towards locally cooler places, while in areas of cooling, trajectories show isotherm shifts towards locally warmer areas.

Trajectory classes across the velocity maps were evaluated by obtaining counts of trajectories that started, ended and crossed 0.2-degree grid cells. For comparison with the earlier study, done globally at a 1-degree resolution, trajectory counts were aggregated in a 1-degree neighbourhood around each grid cell. The aggregated counts were then used to calculate the proportions of cells that started, ended and flowed through the cells in the neighbourhood, and used to classify cells using the methods of Burrows *et al.* (2014), also described in Burrows *et al.* (2025).

The scripts used for the analyses described in this report, along with the adapted version of the *VoCC* package (García Molinos *et al.*, 2019), are available in the GitHub repository: https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_climatevelocity.

Results

Maps of the velocity of climate change follow the patterns of spatial gradients and temporal trends in temperature (Figure 1). Velocity is positive where the temporal trend in temperature is warming (Figure 3) and negative when cooling. Higher velocities emerge where spatial gradients in temperature are shallow, as in the North Sea (Figure 4) and lower where gradients are steep, as along coastlines with strong upwelling in Portugal and Morocco. Across all SSP scenarios, highest velocities are projected for the southern Atlantic region, the Mediterranean, the North Sea and the Baltic. Lowest values for the magnitude of velocity, including negative values, are seen in an area of cooling south of Iceland and west of Scotland and Ireland and locally with steep spatial gradients in temperature.

Broad similarities are apparent between velocity maps across all periods (Figure 1), as expected given the consistency patterns of projected warming and cooling (Figure 3) and especially of spatial gradients of temperature across all scenarios (Figure 4). All but the most extreme end of century scenarios (SSP370 and SSP585 2080-2100) shows a large area of negative velocity in an area of projected cooling west of Ireland. High velocity areas in the North Sea, the Mediterranean and areas off Scandinavia. While the sign (negative or positive) of velocity is driven by the sign of temperature trends, the magnitude of velocity is strongly influenced by the spatial gradients in temperature. Directions of the velocity of climate are also very similar across all the scenarios (Figure 2), except where the trend in temperature over time switches from negative to positive in the most-extreme scenarios (SSP370 and SSP585 2080-2100) in the offshore north Atlantic where the direction shifts from equatorwards to polewards. Since spatial gradients are driven by oceanographic features that

are expected to persist over time, such correspondence in patterns of magnitude and directions of velocity particularly is expected.

Maps of the classification of trajectory behaviour (Figure 5, see Table 1 for definitions) also show similarities across all the SSP scenarios. Climate ‘sources’, areas where no direct connections exist to warmer places to allow species distributions to expand, are found offshore in the centres of regional seas as in the Mediterranean and North Sea or offshore between locally cool coastal areas and even cooler ocean regions, as off the coast of northern Spain. As climate trajectories lengthen with increasing velocity and duration of simulations, source areas tend to emerge just offshore along poleward facing coasts. The extents of non-moving and slow-moving areas declines while those of convergence and divergence increases with the same patterns of increasing velocity. Non- and slow-moving areas dominate the map for SSP1-1.9 2040-2060 but are almost non-existent for SSP5-8.5 2080-2100.

Discussion

Maps produced in this project represent an advance on earlier versions of climate velocity maps for European seas (Burrows *et al.*, 2011, 2014) being at much higher resolution: 0.1-degree latitude and longitude resolution for trajectories and 0.2-degree resolution for climate trajectory classes. However, the higher resolution does change spatial patterns of velocity at smaller scales. Climate velocity has been shown in other studies to be very scale-dependent, particularly on land, with local variations in temperature driving speed and direction of velocity towards local features, such as mountains, at high resolutions and geographical-scale variations in temperature driving directions generally polewards at larger scales (Dobrowski *et al.*, 2013). This effect is evident in the velocity maps for the recent (1950-2010, Figure 7) and current periods (2010-2050, Figure 6). Earlier analysis using 1-degree data (e.g. [Hadley Centre Sea Ice and Sea Surface Temperature Dataset \(HadISST\) v1.1](#) in Burrows *et al.*, 2011) showed similar rapid velocities in the North Sea (>20 km/yr), for example, that were generally poleward (Figure 3a, Burrows *et al.*, 2014). For example, velocity maps at 0.1-degree (Figure 6, Figure 7) show broadly similar large scale geographical patterns in speed of climate shifts, with rapid velocities in the North Sea, but very different directions, particularly in coastal areas where climate velocity is mostly oriented towards locally cooler coastlines. Such local spatial variation is averaged out at larger spatial scales. The implications for shifts in species distributions of these differences in outcomes at different spatial resolution will require careful consideration in terms of their impact on biodiversity (Table 1). They may indicate locations where there will be little or no temperature change and which may be considered thermal refugia, and areas with relatively high warming which may see changes in species’ abundance due to climate warming. Patterns of changing velocity and trajectory across the SSP scenarios show how much more complex and wide ranging the effects of shifting species distributions will be on biodiversity across European seas with increasing intensity and duration of climate warming.

A full discussion and matching of patterns seen here and their associations with patterns of biodiversity, blue carbon reserves and the European MPA network will appear in later deliverables for MPA Europe.

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Table 1. Summary of trajectory classes, with implications for species range shifts if species distributions track shifting climatic niches. Descriptions of climate sources and sinks, and their effects are for warming regions (from Burrows *et al.*, 2014).

Trajectory class	Climate connectivity	Effects on population distributions	Effects on species richness
Climate Sources	Disconnected from warmer locales	High emigration. No climate immigration.	Species richness declines as climate emigrants not replaced.
Climate Sinks	Disconnected from cooler locales	Species have no adjacent cooler place to relocate. No climate emigration. High climate immigration.	Local extirpation possible, but lost species replaced. Richness stable.
Climate Corridors	Pathways of strong or intense isotherm movement	Species arriving from geographically distant locations. High emigration and immigration.	Richness stable or increased.
Convergence and Divergence	Areas where isotherms gather or disperse	Moderate emigration and immigration	Richness change depends on balance of emigrants and immigrants.
Low-velocity Areas	Climate change does not propagate rapidly across the surface	Little, or slow change in species composition and distribution.	Little change.

Figure 1. Climate velocity maps of sea surface temperature (SST) for Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) ensemble models for four Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). Plots show the magnitude of climate velocity in km/yr for periods beginning in 2000-2020 and ending in (top row) 2040-2060 and (bottom row) 2080-2100. Negative velocities arise in areas of projected cooling over the scenario period.

Figure 2. Maps of the direction of climate velocity maps of sea surface temperature (SST) for Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) ensemble models for four Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). Plots show the direction of climate velocity in degrees for periods beginning in 2000-2020 and ending in (top row) 2040-2060 and (bottom row) 2080-2100. Pink is moving northwards; blue, eastwards; yellow, westwards; green, southwards.

Figure 3. Sea surface temperature (SST) trend maps in °C/year (blue cooling, red warming, grey little change) for Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) ensemble models for four Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). Maps show projected rate of change in temperature between 2000-2020 and (top row) 2040-2060 and (bottom row) 2080-2100.

Figure 4. Maps of the average spatial gradients of sea surface temperature (SST) from four Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) scenarios between 2000-2020 and (top row) 2040-2060 and (bottom row) 2080-2100. Plots show the magnitude of spatial gradients in SST in °C/km.

Figure 5. Climate velocity trajectory classes for climate velocity of sea surface temperature in European seas, based on projected climate change under four Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). Maps show classifications of trajectories from 2000-2020 to (top row) 2040-2060 and (bottom row) 2080-2100. Maps are derived from climate trajectories as shown as in **Figure 6** and **Figure 7**.

Figure 6. Velocity of climate change for sea surface temperature in European seas, based on projected climate change under Shared Socioeconomic Pathway SSP3-7.0 from 2000-2020 to 2040-2060. Lines show climate velocity trajectories: the shifts in points of given temperature over the 40-year period from their start at the centre of grid cells in 2010 to their end in 2050, moving annually at the pace of local velocity. The magnitude of climate velocity is shown by the underlying colour: red in areas of high velocity, yellow in low or zero velocity and green to blue in areas of negative velocity where temperatures are projected to cool.

Figure 7. Climate velocity trajectory classes for climate velocity of sea surface temperature in European seas, based on projected climate change under Shared Socioeconomic Pathway SSP1-1.9 from 2000-2020 to 2040-2060. Climate trajectories are shown as in **Figure 6**.

Appendix

Figure A1. Maps of (A) present and future projected actual annual mean sea surface temperatures (SST), i.e., Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (B) SSP1-1.9, (C) SSP2-4.5, (D) SSP3-7.0, (E) SSP4-6.0, (F) SSP5-8.5.

Figure A2. Maps of (A) present and future projected annual mean sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies, i.e. Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (B) SSP1-1.9, (C) SSP2-4.5, (D) SSP3-7.0, (E) SSP4-6.0, (F) SSP5-8.5.

